

PRINCIPLE OF SEPARATION OF POWERS: THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL PROBLEMS

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Annotation: In this article, the origin of the state, its functions and principles as the main category of the science of state and legal theory, in particular, the principle of dividing the state into legislative, executive and judicial power, its meaning, significance, today's importance, theoretical analysis of this principle and practical examples. will be considered.

Key words: state, society, legislature, executive, judiciary, law, law enforcement

Introduction. Principle of separation of powers to date is realized in most states of the modern world. This principle allows providing the rational functioning of state power. Also, by embodiment of principle of powers' division, provided rights and freedoms of citizens that will be realized in socio-economic and political life of society. Plenary powers and functions of three branches of power determine their mutual relations inter se and role of each of them in the political system of state power. In opinion of french scientist M. Duverje: "Any constitution draws not one, but many schemes of government, the construction of which depends on the distribution of forces between the branches of government "[1, p. 10]. Principle of separation of powers must answer the necessities of society and take into account the sociocultural and economic aspects of population.

Main part. Globalization and transformation of democratic values on a higher level affront to revise principle of separation of powers to not only the developing countries but also countries that are the founders of modern democratic society, such as the USA, Germany, France, Great Britain etc. The mechanisms of realization of principle of division of authorities that depend mainly on the form of rule are created

in modern democratic countries. In our view, it would be expedient to consider modern world progress of principle of division of authorities trends in presidential, semi presidential and parliamentary countries individually. [3:1]

In history, there are two main types of republican forms of government – the presidential and parliamentary republics. The United States of America can be considered as the classical form of the presidential republic. Created as the result of the war for independence of the North American colonies, the United States was not only the first independent state in the New World, but also the first presidential republic in the world. Now many states of the world have adopted the American model of the presidential republic, the institution of presidency that arose on the American continent more than two centuries ago gradually gained new spaces for itself. The presidential republic is now the main form of new independent states of the post-Soviet space, so it is extremely important for them to investigate the specifics of the emergence and evolution of the presidential form of government in the United States. [2:3]

Separation of powers is one of the basic structural principles of democratic societies. It was already discussed by ancient philosophers; deep analysis can be found in medieval political and philosophical scientific work. We base our contemporary discussion on legal theory that has been developed in parallel to the emergence of democratic systems in Northern America and in Europe in the 18th century. [3:2]

In presidential countries a head of the state simultaneously is the head of government, parliament is formed directly from the side of population by means of elections (or indirect in case of the USA) by direct vote, and a department judicial is formed on the consent of two branches of power, id est president and parliament. In the USA President presents executive power individually, in turn unaccountable to Congress and bears the responsibility only before people. Mutual relations between President and Congress in the USA have the special character. Vice- President, being the deputy of head of the state, simultaneously is the chairman of Senate, that gives to President an "invisible" instrument in having influence on Congress. The president of the USA has a row of plenary powers, in accordance with that the head of the state on

the consent of Congress appoints the leaders of federal executive branches (ministers), has a right to apply a veto or partial veto (on the separate norms of law) on the laws accepted by Congress. Further President is not right to dismiss Congress, but the last can dismiss the head of the state by impeachment. Impeachment is also used Congress in relation to the public servants of federal level and judges, where a lower chamber (House of representatives) pulls out prosecutions, and Senate gets a right to judge and award judgement. Further President is not right to dismiss Congress, but the last can dismiss the head of the state by impeachment. Impeachment is also used Congress in relation to the public servants of federal level and judges, where a lower chamber (House of representatives) pulls out prosecutions, and Senate gets a right to judge and award judgement. A president, annually coming forward on the incorporated meeting of two chambers, directs in Congress a message that along with informing the members of parliament about internal and external position, plugs in itself recommendations for the acceptance of certain laws (it can be named original legislative initiative of President).[4:1]

When we combine the concept of the separation of powers with the independence of constitutional courts, we address two different aspects. The first aspect has just been mentioned. The independence of constitutional courts is an objective of the separation of powers; independence is its result. This is the first aspect and perhaps the aspect which first occurs to most of us. The second aspect deals with the reverse relationship: independence of constitutional courts as a precondition for the separation of powers. Independence enables constitutional courts to effectively control the respect for the separation of powers.

Separation of powers is not an end in itself, nor is it a simple tool for legal theorists or political scientists. It is a basic principle in every democratic society that serves other purposes such as freedom, legality of state acts and independence of certain organs that exercise power delegated to them by a specific constitutional rule.

Conclusion. Based on the above, it can be concluded that in today's conditions, i.e., in the context of digitalization, every process that takes place in the life of society

and the state is waiting for a high-level solution to its theoretical and practical problems. The principle of separation of powers, in particular, the mutual restraint of the legislative, executive and judicial powers, the need for each branch to exercise its own powers, for example, the non-interference of one power with the powers of another power problem is considered one of the issues that need to be solved today. In finding a solution to this problem, the use of established national traditions and foreign experience will give effective results.

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